

Effect of Problem - Based Strategy on Performance in Concept Ecosystem Among Secondary School Students In Zaria Educational Zone, Kaduna State

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Abstract

This paper investigated the effects of problem - based strategy on performance in concept ecosystem among secondary school students in Zaria Educational Zone, Kaduna State. Problem based instructional strategy is relatively new hence the need to ascertain to what extent it would assist at improving the performance of secondary school students in concept ecosystem in geography. A lot of concerns have hitherto before now been raised by stakeholders on how instructional strategy have been a major challenge to high performance by students in geography. This has necessitated the call for a paradigm change from the traditional method to the one being investigated in this work. It was on this note that its effect is being investigated before long. A total number of three (3) research objectives, research questions and hypotheses each were formulated in this study. The research design used in this study was quasi experimental research, using researcher designed Geography Achievement test. The target population for this study was comprised of five thousand, five hundred and forty - eight (5,548) SS II students from Zaria Educational Zone. A sample size of three hundred and fifty - seven (357) respondents was therefore selected at random using simple sampling technique for the study. It thus represented two (2) study schools with two (2) classes of students from SS II involved in this study, one was the controlled group (conventional method) and the other, is the experimental group (problem - based strategy). Sole instrument used in this study was validated and adjudged reliable via Cronbach alpha (α) reliability, reliability co - efficient scores obtained for the instrument was 0.882. Data analyses were undertaken through the use of inferential statistics. Kruskal Wallis, Independent t - test and one way analysis of variance statistics were used in the testing of hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level of significance. The findings of this study revealed that there is significant effect of problem - based strategy on performance in concept ecosystem among secondary school students in Zaria Educational Zone, Kaduna State. In addition, the study revealed that significant gender difference exists in the effect of problem - based strategy on performance in concept ecosystem among secondary school students in Zaria Educational Zone, Kaduna State. In conclusion, significant effect of problem - based strategy resulted to increase in performance of secondary school students in concept ecosystem. The study therefore recommended that the use of problem - based strategy should be encouraged among geography teachers through constant supervision. That Geography teacher should be motivated to using these modern methods of teaching through sponsorship to workshops and in - house trainings.

Keywords: *Academic Performance, Effects, Geography, Problem - Based Learning*

Introduction

The important role of teachers in the teaching - learning process in and around the schools cannot be underestimated. Teachers are noted to play a lot of influences in their classroom practices. They therefore need to apply specific abilities and skills without which their influence may not reflect in students' performance in their subject. Consequently, the need to use appropriate and effective instructional strategy to make students easily transfer what is taught in schools and apply such to solve problems in real life situation has become imperative. The teaching of concept ecosystem has featured in Geography before now was popular with the traditional approach that is gradually fading out (Getso & Haruna, 2021). This perhaps could be due to poor performance of students in Geography generally as attested to, by various external reports of West African

Effect of Problem - Based ... (Bara'u, et. al., 2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11401649>

Examinations Council and other bodies. Bearing this in mind, the need to explore other instructional method such as problem - based learning which is relatively new has become essential. Problem - based learning (PBL) is a well - established learner centred and inquiry - oriented instructional strategy. Rosing in Hirca cited by Idris (2023) explained that students in a PBL classroom try to look for information, access learning material and share ideas among themselves while working in small groups. PBL is new from the known traditional method of teaching. Perhaps, since there is an alarming outcry that teachers tend to dominate the whole classroom activities, making the learners passive listeners, inactive and dull. Also, making the teaching process unlively, uninteresting, unproductive, unreal and less permanent in the learners' mind in most cases.

Therefore, an alarming call for a shift from the common, olden days traditional teacher - centred method of teaching to a more productive learner centred, activity centred, child centred or experienced centred approach for improved performance by the students. According to Adedokun & Jamu cited by Idris (2015), Geography is an old discipline from the basis of human knowledge about his environment, the world and his relationship with the element of environment. In view of this, Geography can be viewed as a subject that focuses on disciplinary change and paradigm shift which makes the use of appropriate teaching method important for its teaching and learning. The need for the use of problem - based strategy (PBS) in concept ecosystem in Geography stems from the belief that it is an abstract subject that needs to be centralized for students to appreciate as a school subject. Geography as a school subject is very important and useful to students and everyone who seeks to cope with the ever - emerging realities of the present time. This is because the earth which is the focus of geography study is the theater where virtually all human activities are carried out. And it is only reasonable that man knows about the nature and character of the earth, as well as the consequences of interactions between man and his environment. The above concept had further lend itself to varied meanings by different scholars, among which are Akintade (2011); Abidoye & Ogunniyi (2012) and Idris (2015).

Academic performance on the other hand represents learning outcomes that indicate the extent to which a person has accomplished specific goals that were the focus of activities in instructional environments, specifically in school, college, and university. As observed by the researchers, every individual is born with certain potentialities and peculiarities, but it is the teacher that helps bring out such potentialities in the learners. Ability of the teacher to dominate the class activities makes the learners idle, the lesson bored and the environment dull. For improved performance in learners' academics, the teachers' roles have to embrace learning by doing, making the lesson lively and interactive too. Learner's participation is encouraged such that all will be carried along in the entire teaching process. By so doing, students' performance tends to improve and more investments can be committed to it by the different stakeholders. The sad scenario however is, most geography teachers don't display such skills in their teaching. This calls for research such as the present one being conceived.

Concept of Performance

Academic performance is determined by many factors and it thus means the extent to which a student, teacher, or institution has attained their short or long-term educational goals. It is measured either by continuous assessment or cumulative grade point average of a student (Talib & Sansgiry, 2012). Some of these factors include teachers' subject mastery, textbooks availability and accessibility, libraries, practical laboratory and many other factors (Chinyoka & Naidu, 2013). Performance could also mean "achievement" in a course taught by the teacher reflecting the quality and quantity of a student's work during a given period". Academic performance thus represents learning outcomes that indicate the extent to which a person has accomplished specific goals that were the focus of activities in instructional environments, specifically in school, college, or university. The field of academic achievement which can be used interchangeably is wide-ranging and covers a broad variety of educational outcomes.

Academic performance of learners has in recent times attracted the attention of scholars, parents, policy-makers and planners. This was because the amount of investment by governments and parents on schools and learners are far what is obtainable now. Quality education, manpower and infrastructural facilities that do not justify what is on ground. Suneetha & Mayuri (2001) in their contributions opine that the major goal of the school is to work towards attainment of academic excellence by students. According to them, the school may have other peripheral objectives; emphasis is thus always placed on the performance of students in and outside the school settings. Besides, virtually everybody concerned with education places much premium on academic performance; excellent academic performance by children is often the expectation of parents..

Concept of Problem Based Learning (PBL)

PBL is an instructional (and curricular) learner - centered approach that empowers learners to conduct research, integrate theory and practice, and apply knowledge and skills to develop a viable solution to a definite problem. PBL is further described as an educational strategy where learning is driven by a problem. The problem could be a challenge or a description of a difficulty, a curious outcome, or an unexpected happening. It could also be an incident where there are interesting elements or an episode or occurrence that requires either a solution or some explanation. PBL as an educational strategy assists the

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students to take up responsibility for their own learning. In the teaching profession, the ability to direct and regulate one's own learning experience is crucial to its success.

PBL facilitates not only the acquisition and organization of knowledge, but also the development of several other desirable attributes, such as communication skills, teamwork, problem-solving skills, self-directed learning, sharing of information and identification of personal strengths and weaknesses (Neville, 1999 in Williams, 2001).

Statement of the Research Problem

Geography is one of the activity - based school subject offered at the senior secondary school levels. It has however, been observed that many Geography teachers still use old instructional strategy that are ineffective and cannot meet the needs of the twenty - first century learners. This is contrary to what is expected or could deliver better results and responses from students in terms of their interest and performance in geography. Bearing this in mind, there is a need to employ a better and more suitable method of teaching as anticipated in problem - based learning (PBL). In the past, teaching used to be teacher - centred, where the teacher takes the lead and is at the centre of classroom activities. It is important to stress that there is thus a paradigm shift in the twenty first century classroom from teacher - centred to learner- centered approach. Although, efforts put in place by teachers to effectively teach geography in Nigerian secondary schools is not satisfactory when compared with students' performance in the subject. To further buttress this point, the report of external examiners of West African Examinations Council (WAEC) and National Examinations Council (NECO) for May 2016 and thereafter indicated that the students performed poorly in geography (Mohenty, 2016). Studies have further shown a decline in students' performance in science and geography in particular and this has been attributed to the fact that strategies of teaching used in classrooms are not very effective (Bichi in Kawu, Arabi and Murtala, 2023). Obviously, students' performance is being used as one of the predictors of overall quality of education system. To this end, Usman (2018) stated that the quality of education that teachers provide to students is dependent upon what the teachers do in the classroom. Sanlera (2016) pointed out that despite the existence of learning theories (detailing how people learn), most teacher still dispense information using traditional methods without regard to students learning activities. It was on account of all this, that study on effects of problem - based strategy on performance in concept ecosystem among secondary school students in Zaria Educational Zone, Kaduna State has become imperative.

Purpose of the Study

The study assessed effects of problem - based strategy on performance in concept ecosystem among secondary school students in Zaria Educational Zone, Kaduna State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the mean performance score of secondary school Geography students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Zaria Educational Zone.
2. Determine the mean performance score of secondary school Geography male and female students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy in Zaria Educational Zone.
3. Determine the interactive effect of mean performance score of secondary school Geography male and female students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy in Zaria Educational Zone.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study.

1. What is the mean performance score of secondary school Geography students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Zaria Educational Zone?
2. What is the mean performance score of secondary school Geography male and female students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy in Zaria Educational Zone?
3. What is the interactive effects of mean performance score of secondary school Geography male and female students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy in Zaria Educational Zone?

Hypotheses

The following null - hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 alpha level of significance.

HO₁ There is no significant difference between mean performance score of secondary school Geography students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Zaria Educational Zone.

HO₂ There is no significant difference between mean performance score of secondary school Geography male and female students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy in Zaria Educational Zone.

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HO₃ There is no significant interactive between mean performance score of secondary school Geography male and female students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy in Zaria Educational Zone.

Methodology

This study adopted quasi - experimental research design. It thus connotes that two (2) groups exists namely experimental and controlled groups. Students were taught using different instructional strategies (lecture and problem-based) under the different groups with a view to ascertain what their performances would be. The controlled group (lecture method) is for SS II students of GSS K/Kuyanbana while the experimental group (problem - based learning) covered SS II students of Government Commercial College, Zaria. Treatment was given to the experimental group alone since it is the focal point for this study. The choice of the two (2) selected schools was supported by this type of research design been undertaken. It does not allow for the selection of many schools since it is experimental in nature. The target population of this study was comprised of eight hundred and eleven (811) Geography students from the selected senior secondary schools of Zaria Educational Zone, Kaduna State. A sample size of three hundred and fifty - seven (357) respondents was selected at random from the targeted population. In view of this, only SS II students offering Geography as a school subject were involved in this study. The study employed the use of achievement test as sole instrument for data collection. A pilot study was carried out in Government Secondary School, Muchia using forty (40) geography students of equal proportion of both sexes. The reliability test scores for the instrument was 0.882 for the achievement test. Permission was sought from the Inspectorate Division Data collection was undertaken within ten (10) weeks. Research assistants were identified, trained and motivated on how to assist in the administration of instrument. The data analysis was carried out on the formulated hypotheses using inferential statistics such as t - test statistics, one way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and descriptive means statistics at 0.05 alpha level of significance for acceptance or rejection.

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1

What is the mean performance score of secondary school Geography students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Zaria Educational Zone?

Table 1: Descriptive statistics effect of problem - based instructional strategy on concept ecosystem on students' performance in Zaria Educational Zone of Kaduna State

Variable	Groups	N	Mean	SD	MD	Remarks
Performance	Experimental	202	50.83	10.23		Problem based learning has positive effect on students' performance
	Control	156	44.46	7.77	6.370	

Source: Field Work (2023)

The descriptive statistics above showed that Problem based strategy has positive effect on performance of secondary school students in concept ecosystem in the Zone. Their computed mean performance scores are 50.8292 and 44.4583 by experimental and control group respectively in favour of the experimental group who were exposed to the problem- based strategy implying a positive effect on performance in the concept ecosystem as one of the topics in geography.

Research Question 2

What is the mean performance score of secondary school Geography male and female students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy in Zaria Educational Zone?

Table 2: Descriptive mean statistics on mean performance score of secondary school Geography male and female students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy in Zaria Educational Zone in Kaduna State

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Variable	Gender groups	N	Mean	SD	MD	Remarks
Academic Performance	Exp (Male)	132	56.1061	9.91741		The mean performance scores of experimental male and female groups are far higher than those of male and female mean score of control group
	Exp (Female)	69	57.3623	10.47963		
	Control (Male)	107	45.5047	10.35718		
	Control (Female)	49	40.5306	8.41403		

Source: Field Work (2023)

The results of above descriptive statistics showed that there is positive effect of problem - based strategy on gender and students' performance in concept ecosystem in geography in the Zone. The experimental male and experimental female performance mean scores are 56.1061 and 57.3623, while control male and control female performance scores are 45.5047 and 40.5306 respectively. This shows that both experimental male and experimental female have remarkable higher mean scores than their counterparts in the control group.

Research Question 3

What is the interactive effects of mean performance score of secondary school Geography male and female students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy in Zaria Educational Zone?

Table 3: Descriptive statistics on interactive effects of Problem-based strategy on mean performance of secondary school Geography male and female students taught concept Ecosystem in Zaria Educational Zone in Kaduna State

Groups	Gender	N	Mean	STD
Experimental	Male	132	50.4545	9.96644
	Female	69	51.8623	10.47963
	Total	201	50.9378	10.14149
Control	Male	107	45.6075	7.50347
	Female	49	41.9490	7.87880
	Total	156	44.4583	7.78646
Total	Male	239	48.2845	9.25109
	Female	118	47.7458	10.64717
	Total	357	48.1064	9.72298

Source: Field Work (2023)

Results in table 3 above showed that there was interactive effect of problem - based strategy on male and female geography students using ecosystem in the Zone where the study was conducted. The computed mean statistics showed that at the experimental group the computed mean performance scores are 50.454 and 51.862 for male and female geography students respectively, while at the control group the computed mean performance score are 45.807 and 41.949 for male and female geography students also. Invariably, this shows that there was an interactive effect of the problem - based strategy on male and female geography taught ecosystem in Zaria Educational Zone of Kaduna State.

Hypotheses Testing

Ho1: There is no significant difference between mean performance score of secondary school Geography students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Zaria Educational Zone.

Table 4: Independent t - test statistics on effect of problem - based strategy on performance in concept ecosystem among secondary school students in Zaria Educational Zone of Kaduna State

Variable	Groups	N	Mean	SD	MD	df	T-Cal	T-Crit	P-value
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	Expr	202	50.8292	10.233					
Performance					6.37087	356	6.463	1.96	0.000
	Cntrl	156	44.4583	7.786					

Source: Field Work (2023) *p value < 0.05, t cal> 1.96 at df 356*

Outcome of the independent t - test statistics revealed that there was significant difference on the effect of problem - based strategy and performance of students in concept ecosystem in geography in Zaria Educational Zone of Kaduna state. The calculated p value of 0.000 is lower than the 0.05 alpha level of significance and their t calculated value of 6.370 is higher than the 1.96 t critical value at df 356. Their computed mean performance scores are 50.8292 and 44.4583 for experimental and controlled groups respectively in favour of experimental group who were exposed to the problem-based strategy implying a positive effect on performance in concept ecosystem in geography. Therefore, null hypothesis which says there is no significant difference between mean performance score of secondary school Geography students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Zaria Educational Zone is hereby rejected.

HO₂ There is no significant difference between mean performance score of secondary school Geography male and female students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy in Zaria Educational Zone.

Table 5: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) statistics on significant difference between mean performance score of secondary school Geography male and female students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy in Zaria Educational Zone of Kaduna State

Variable	Gender groups	N	Mean	SD	MD	df	f-cal	f-crit	PValue
Academic Performance	Exp (Male)	132	56.1061	9.917					
	Exp (Female)	69	57.3623	10.480					
	Control (Male)	107	45.5047	10.357		3	49.705	2.60	0.000
	Control (Female)	49	40.5306	8.414					

Source: Field Work (2023) *P calculated < 0.05, f calculated > f critical at df 3*

The results of Analysis of variance (ANOVA) statistics showed that there was significant difference between mean performance score of secondary school Geography male and female students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy in Zaria Educational Zone of Kaduna state. Reasons being that the calculated p value of 0.000 is lower than the 0.05 alpha level of significance. The experimental male and experimental female performance scores are 56.1061 and 57.3623, while controlled male and controlled female performance scores are 45.5047 and 40.5306 respectively. This shows that both experimental male and female groups have significantly higher mean scores than their counterparts in the controlled group. The null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between mean performance score of secondary school Geography male and female students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy in Zaria Educational Zone of Kaduna State, is hereby *rejected*.

HO₃ There is no significant interactive between mean performance score of secondary school Geography male and female students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy in Zaria Educational Zone.

Table 6: Descriptive mean statistics on interactive effect of secondary school Geography male and female students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy in Zaria Educational Zone of Kaduna State

Groups	Gender	Mean	STD	N
Experimental	Male	50.4545	9.96644	132
	Female	51.8623	10.47963	69
	Total	50.9378	10.14149	201
Control	Male	45.6075	7.50347	107
	Female	41.9490	7.87880	49

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	Total	44.4583	7.78646	156
Total	Male	48.2845	9.25109	239
	Female	47.7458	10.64717	118
	Total	48.1064	9.72298	357

Source: Field Work (2023)

Results of the above table 6 showed that there was significant interactive effect of problem - based strategy on gender and students' performance in concept ecosystem in geography in Zaria Educational Zone of Kaduna State. This was on account that at the groups versus gender levels, the calculated p-value of 0.015 is lower than the 0.05 alpha level of significance and the t calculated value of 5.941 is greater than the 3.00 F critical value at df 1. The computed mean statistics showed that at the experimental group the computed mean performance scores are 50.454 and 51.862 for male and female geography students respectively, while at the controlled group the computed mean performance scores are 45.807 and 41.949 for male and female geography students also. This was an evident that there was an interactive effect of problem - based strategy on gender and students' performance in concept ecosystem in geography in Zaria Educational Zone of Kaduna State. Therefore, the null hypothesis which showed that there is no no significant interactive between mean performance score of secondary school Geography male and female students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy in Zaria Educational Zone of Kaduna State is hereby rejected.

Summary of Major Findings

The followings are the major findings of this study.

1. Significant difference exists in the mean performance score of secondary school Geography students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Zaria Educational Zone.
2. There is significant difference between mean performance score of secondary school Geography male and female students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy in Zaria Educational Zone.
3. There was significant interactive difference in the mean performance score of secondary school Geography male students when compared with their female counterparts taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy in Zaria Educational Zone.

Discussions of Findings

This study assessed the effects of problem - based strategy on performance in concept ecosystem among secondary school students in Zaria Educational Zone, Kaduna State. A total of three (3) null hypotheses were tested in line with the specific objectives and research questions of the study. In hypothesis I, significant difference between mean performance score of secondary school Geography students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Zaria Educational Zone was tested. The result of the test conducted using t - test statistics revealed that the respondents were of the opinion that problem - based strategy was of significant effect on performance of secondary school students in concept ecosystem in geography in the study area. The null hypothesis was therefore rejected on account of this. The finding here concurred with Wright, Horn & Sanders (1997) that the most important factor influencing student learning is the teacher.

Teachers stand in the interface of the transmission of knowledge, values and skills in the learning process. If the teacher is ineffective, students under the teacher's tutelage will achieve inadequate progress academically. This is regardless of how similar or different the students are in terms of individual potential in academic achievement. Since PBL was found to have positive effect on students' academic achievement and that the teacher plays a vital role in actualizing that, geography teachers need to be conversant with this learning strategy so that they should employ it in their instructional process for effectiveness and efficiency, as well as ensuring high academic performance. It is one thing to know the strategy, another thing is to have the technical know - how on when and where to apply it having improved this on the teachers. It is assumed that students' concentration and achievement in class performance, end of term examination, promotion examination and final year examination with improve to the positive. This position concurs with that of research question I with PBL having a positive effect on students' achievement.

Null hypothesis II tested the significant difference between mean performance score of secondary school Geography male and female students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy in Zaria Educational Zone of Kaduna State. The result of the test revealed that there was significant difference in performances of male and female geography students taught concept ecosystem in geography in Kaduna State. The null hypothesis formulated in this regard was therefore accepted

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and rejected. The findings here agreed with Adeyemi (2010) and Yala & Wanjohi (2011) who found out that teachers' experience and educational qualifications are the prime predictors of students' academic achievement irrespective of their gender affiliations. In science education, attitude toward science is an important factor affecting both male and female students' science achievement as well as students' alternative conceptions and misconceptions.

It is a clear indication from the analysis that PBL is gender friendly. Meaning that both male and female students liked the approach that is, why it doesn't indicate any change or difference in their academic attitudes. Geography teachers being just and sincere need to embrace this approach so that equal treatment and attention can be given to the students. Despite the extroertic nature of male and introbatic nature of female, the PBL seemed highly appropriate and suitable to diagnose, handle, guide, direct, assist and counsel students' attitudes to the positive for better and stable behavior and conducive learning environment. As teachers' experience and qualification form an integral part of moulding students' behavior, they should be up and doing in serving as parents, friends as well as role model who inspires his students for better interest and positive attitudes. Besides, research question IV concurred that positive effect exists between gender and students' attitude to Geography as far as the use of PBL is concerned in the classrooms.

In null hypothesis III, significant interactive effect between mean performance score of secondary school Geography male and female students taught concept Ecosystem using Problem-based strategy in Zaria Educational Zone of Kaduna State was tested. The result revealed that the two variables were significantly correlated against one another viz - a - viz the significant interactive effect of male and female secondary school geography students taught concept ecosystem in the study area. The null hypothesis was therefore rejected. The finding here is a reflection of statement credited to Zhou, Huang & Tian (2013) who concluded that tasked - based learning improves student's analytical skills and ability to personalize learning. Students are able to evaluate and infer into contents learnt while making reasonable conclusion. In their own contributions, Sungur & Tekkaya (2006) asserted that the use of PBL is found to enhance self - regulatory skills in students thereby improving academic performance. The students are able to explore other ways of learning through the use of PBL.

Students' interactivity with learning and learning materials is the demand of learner centeredness. Observations from this study equally revealed that when students are exposed to identifying problems by themselves and solving that problem according to their peculiarities and differences, such interaction makes learning meaningful, interacting, real and permanent in them. What they have done will stay permanent and can easily be recalled at anytime the need arises. The same approach can make them think critically and have diversified approaches to handling similar problems on their own without teacher's guide. Geography teachers should take that as a challenge for them to study and master this approach thoroughly when applied to their lessons for effective and efficient instructional process, as well as improvement on student's academic achievement.

Conclusion

It can be deduced from the analysis of data and hypotheses tested for this study that problem-based strategy no doubt has improved the performances of students taught concept ecosystem in geography. This may not be limited to schools used for this study alone but across to other secondary schools if same instructional strategy is adopted. Also, there was significant difference between performances of male and female geography students taught concept ecosystem in secondary schools of the study Zone. Absolutely, problem-based strategy stands as a better method of teaching when compared with the lecture method. It is therefore essential that its use be encouraged across all school subjects by teachers for which higher performances are targeted.

Recommendations

The following are the recommendations put forward as a result of the outcome of this study:

1. The use of problem- based learning strategy should be encouraged among geography teachers through constant supervision of the geography teachers.
2. The attitude of the students can be further enhanced in geography lesson by proper monitoring of the students by involving the students in the lesson.
3. Geography teachers should be provided all the necessary teaching facilities and infrastructures such as teaching aids and conducive learning environment.

Acknowledgements

The researchers wish to express their gratitude to the management of Federal College of Education, Zaria for finding us worthy and capable of carrying out this research work. In the same vein, TETFUND as an intervention agency of government is deeply appreciated for the numerous assistance provided to our College and others at large. Also, the efforts of the lead researcher is

Effect of Problem - Based ... (Bara'u, et. al., 2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11401649>

appreciated as well as other researchers for the team work put together at carrying out this study. To our data analyst, Mr. Ojo Umoru words cannot express how grateful we are for the job done in the course of data analysis. To our Head, Dr. Uyagu .B. Grace and others too numerous to mention, we are collectively saying thank you for being there for us.

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